

Rural Development Programme in Sonbhadra District: A Case Study

Dr. Rajendra Prasad Jaiswal

Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, B.N. College Patna University, Patna

ABSTRACT

India is a predominantly rural country, and the economic development of the country depends on the economic development of its rural areas. Therefore, the Indian government is currently implementing various schemes for the development of rural areas, with the main objective of achieving the economic and social upliftment of these regions. This study aims to evaluate the impact of government-sponsored scheme in the study area and to determine which scheme people are aware of and what their sources of information.

Keywords: Rural Development, Swarn Jayanti, Grama Swarojagar Yojana, National Rural Health,
Received : 11/01/2025 **Acceptance :** 25/11/2025

Introduction:

Rural Development is a multi-faced phenomenon in which lies the fate of millions of rural poor in India. India is predominantly an agricultural country and its 68 percent population lives in rural areas with farming as their main occupation. Government has initiated, sustained and refined many rural development programmes as part of the planned growth and development under different Plans. We have discussed the programs that basically aimed at the economic development the families in rural areas. The rural development programmes have focused on rural life. Rural areas are at a great disadvantage, in relation to urban areas, as far as the provision of basic infrastructural facilities and services such as roads, drinking water, electricity, schools, hospitals, police protection, transport and communications is concerned. Not only these public facilities and amenities in rural areas are inadequate, but they are also very poorly organized and undependable. As a result, poor villagers are damned, generation after generation, to poor education, poor health, unemployment and poverty. Improvement of their plight required intensive government intervention.

Study area:

The Sonbhadra district is located in the southern most part of Uttar Pradesh. The study-area lies mainly in the vast Vindhyan plateau tract encompassing the Kaimur scarps, hills, forests and entangled valleys. It covers the North-Eastern part of the Baghelkhand region (a physiographic region of north-central Deccan table land) and exhibits

physico-cultural similarities with Chotanagpur and Sidhi-Panna plateau (central and eastern part of Peninsular foreland) in terms of spatial location and physico-cultural distinctions. Geographical extent of the study area is 23051'20"N-24053'16"N and 82031'55"E-83033'45"E and it extends from north to south to a maximum length of 79.36 km and 74.56 km in East-West direction. It covers an area of 6779 km² including G.B. Pant Sagar reservoir. The study-area is bounded by the districts of Kaimur (Bihar) and Garhwa (Jharkhand) in the East whereas Singrauli and Sidhi district of Madhya-Pradesh form the southern and western boundaries respectively. The two districts of Uttar Pradesh namely, Mirzapur and Chandauli forms the northern boundary of the study-area. Study area divided into eight blocks.

Objective:

The aims and objectives of the proposed paper Rural development plan in sonbhadra district: A geographical study is to assess the rural development of the area. The main objectives are as follows:

To identify the rural development programmes and its status in study area.

Methodology:

Data is the important information for any research. Primary data would be collected with the help of questionnaire to be framed from the selected locations of the study area. Secondary data will be collected from Survey of India, District handbook, Census report, Gazetteer and collected from different

government published data sources related to study area.

Discussion

A survey is conducted in which 2 Village were selected from each block. In this way, some questions asked through questionnaire from 730 houses of total 16 Village, the result of which is clearly shown through the table.

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Act (M.G.N.R.E.G.A.)

MNREGA is an important scheme in the context of India's rural development, in which the right to employment for rural workers was ensured through an act. As per the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005 of the Government of India, 100 days of demand-based

work is allotted in a year to each rural household willing to do unskilled work. On December 31, 2009, the Government of India amended this act and named it Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act.

Objective:

1. Providing 100 days of employment to such families in rural areas during a financial year.
2. Creation of permanent assets in rural areas, which will increase livelihood.
3. To protect the forest, water and environment of the village.
4. Empowerment of women.

The study of MGNREGA scheme started in the area in 2008, since then along with the increase in the income of the beneficiaries, permanent assets were also created.

Table - 1

Response to the question “Are you know the registration of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme

Registration	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	463	63.43
A little To	177	24.24
Much		
No	90	12.33
Total	730	100.00

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question “Are you know the registration of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme?” 63.43% respondents are yes about the Programme, 24.24% respondents are a little to much and 12.33% respondent are no about the Programme. (Table 1)

Table- 2

Response to the question “Source of information Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme

Source of information	No. of Respondents	Percent
Gram Pradhan	426	58.35
Local People	152	20.82
Gram Sewak	87	11.91
Other source	65	08.90
Total	730	100

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question “Source of information Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme?” have been grouped into four categories i.e. Gram Pradhan, local people, Gramsewak and other source. It is analysed that about 58.35 % respondents are Gram Pradhan, 20.82% respondents are local people, 11.91 % respondents are Gramsewak and 08.90% Other source of information gain about the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme (Table 2).

Table -3
Response to the question “Nature of work conduct under MGNREGA?”

Nature of work	No. of Respondents	Percent
Land Development Work	122	16.71
Water Conservation	216	29.58
Irrigation Work	76	10.41
Flood Protection Work		8.92
Road construction		34.38

The responses of the respondents to the question “Nature of work conducted under MGNREGA?” have been grouped into five categories i.e. land development work, water conservation work, irrigation work, Flood protection work and Road construction work. It is analysed that about 16.71% respondents are land development work, 29.58% respondents are water conservation work, 10.41% respondents are 10.41, 08.92 % respondent are Flood protection work and 34.38 % respondent are road construction work engage in the mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme (Table 3).

Table - 4
Response to the question "Meeting family Expenses from The Income Received by Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme?"

Meeting family Expenses from Income Received by MGNREGP	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	186	25.47
A little To much	118	16.16
No	426	58.37
Total	730	100.00

The responses of the respondents to the question “Meeting family Expenses from The Income Received by Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme?” 25.47% respondents are Yes, 16.16% respondents are a little to much and 58.37% respondent are no family expense from the income received by Programme. (Table 4)

Swarn Jayanti Grama Swarojagar Yojana (S.G.S.Y) :

The eradication of poverty has been an integral component of the strategy for economic development in India. High poverty levels are synonymous with poor quality of life, deprivation of basic needs, poor health, malnutrition, illiteracy and low human resource development. Providing employment is the most important method of eradicating poverty. Major employment generation

programmes being implemented in the rural areas have been included under this Point. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act has come into existence for the enhancement of livelihood security of the households in rural areas of the country by providing at least one hundred days of guaranteed wage employment in every financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.

Table - 5

Response to the question “Are you know about the Swarn jayanti Grama Swarojagar Yojana

Know about the S.G.S.Y	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	256	35.06
No	474	64.94
Total	730	100.00

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question “Are you know about the Swarn jayanti Grama Swarojagar Yojana (S.G.S.Y) ?” 35.06% respondents are yes about the programme, and 64.94% respondent have no response about the programme. (Table 5)

Food Security Programme :

For a medium-term strategy for food and nutrition security and to bring out improvements in the food storage facilities, Khadya Suraksha includes items like: i) Public Distribution System, (PDS), ii) Antodya Anna Yojana (AAY), and iii) Establishing Gramin banks in chronically food scarcity areas”. In order to make TPDS more focused and targeted towards BPL population, the Government has restructured the PDS. The AAY and establishment of Gramin Banks aim at ensuring that the poorer segments of the population get food security coverage.

Table - 6

Response to the question “PDS facility is available in your village

PDS facility	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	668	91.50
No	62	08.50
Total	730	100.00

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question “PDS facility is available in your village?” 91.50% respondents are yes and 08.50% respondent are no available PDS facility in my village. (Table 6)

Indira Awas Yojana (I.A.Y.)

The Government is committed to a comprehensive programme for urban renewal and to a massive expansion of housing in towns and cities and also housing for weaker sections in rural area. The Indira Awas Yojana is to provide houses to the houseless poor in Rural areas. Under this scheme, assistance is provided for new construction or for up-gradation of houses for rural houseless BPL families Indira Awas Yojana (I.A.Y)

Table -7

Response to the question “Beneficiary families for housing by Indira Awas Yojana (I.A.Y)?”

Beneficiary families for housing	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	218	29.86
No	512	70.14
Total	730	100.00

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question Beneficiary families for housing by “Indira Awas Yojana?” 29.86% respondents are yes and 70.14% respondent are no Beneficiary families for housing by Indira Awas Yojana. (Table 7)

Programme for Drinking Water Supply : Providing clean drinking water to all households in rural areas and augmenting availability of drinking water sources is priority Government Policy. The main objectives of these programmes are to provide safe drinking water to all villages, assisting local communities to maintain sources of safe drinking water in good condition. Central Rural Sanitation Programme State Governments have the responsibility to provide safe drinking water and sanitation in the rural areas. Government of India supports and supplements the efforts of the State Governments in this regard. under the rural drinking water component of Prime Minister’s Gramodaya Yojna (PMGY-RDW).

Table 8

Response to the question “What are the main source of drinking water supply?”

Water Supply source	No. of Respondents	Percent
Hand pump	379	51.90
Piped water	176	24.10
Well	86	11.78
Ponds	13	01.78
Rivers/another source	76	10.44
Total	730	100

Source : Personal Survey

Regarding the questions related to source of drinking water supply, 51.90% respondents get water from handpump, 24.10% from piped water, 11.78% from well, 01.78% from ponds and 10.44% respondents get water for drinking from rivers water, falls etc.(Table 8)

National Rural Health Mission :

Improvement in the health condition of the population is an essential element of human resource development and of a better quality of life. Government is taking a multi-pronged approach in this vital sector through preventive, promotive and curative measures along with clean drinking water and proper sanitation. It is a fact that productivity has a direct link with health, and it increases as health

care improves Control and Prevention of major diseases. The Plan of Action includes increasing public expenditure on health, reducing regional imbalance in health infrastructure, pooling resources, integration of organizational structures, optimization of health manpower, decantation and district management of health programmes, community participation and ownership of assets, induction of management and financial personnel into district health system, and operationalizing community health centers into functional hospitals meeting Indian Public Health Standards in each Block of the country. The Goal of the Mission is to improve the availability of and access to quality health care by people in rural areas, the poor, women and children.

Table -9

Response to the question “Are you satisfied with health care facilities available in your locality, mention the level of satisfaction?”

Level	No. of Respondents	Percent
Satisfaction	179	24.53
Less satisfied	217	29.72
Not satisfied	334	45.75
Total	730	100

Source : Personal Survey

Regarding the satisfaction with health care facilities only 24.53% respondents were satisfied with the existing facility whereas 29.72 % were less satisfied and 45.75 % were not satisfied with facilities for health care provided in their locality (Table 9).

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan .

Education is one of the priorities for human development and is essential for the country's economic growth. The major indicators of socio-economic development, viz. the growth rate of the

economy, birth rate, death rate, infant mortality rate and literacy rate are all interconnected. The literacy rate has been the major determinant of the other indicators. Efforts are on to eradicate illiteracy in the 15-35 age group and to provide Universal Elementary Education for children up to 14 years. The Mid-day meal scheme is the largest school-nutrition programme in the world. The main objective of the programme is to improve the nutritional status of children.

Table - 10

Response to the question “Where you go for treatment?”

Centers	No. of Respondents	Percent
Sub Centre	117	16.02
Nursing home	86	11.78
Primary Health Centre	187	25.61
Govt. Hospital	226	30.95
Private Clinic	114	15.64
Total	730	100

Source : Personal Survey

Regarding treatment for diseases, 16.02% respondents go to sub-centre, 11.78% at nurs-

ing home, 25.61% at PHC, while 30.95% go to government hospital and 15.64% patients like to go private clinic for their treatment (Table 10).

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan :

Education is one of the priorities for human development and is essential for the country's economic growth. The major indicators of socio-economic development, viz. the growth rate of the economy, birth rate, death rate, infant mortality rate and literacy rate are all interconnected. The literacy rate has been the major determinant of the other indicators. Efforts are on to eradicate illiteracy in the 15-35 age group and to provide Universal Elementary Education for children up to 14 years. The Mid-day meal scheme is the largest school-nutrition programme in the world. The main objective of the programme is to improve the nutritional status of children.

Table 11

Response to the question “Are you satisfied with education facilities available in your locality, mention the level of satisfaction”

Level	No. of Respondents	Percent
Satisfaction	158	21.64
Less satisfied	287	39.32
Not satisfied	285	39.04
Total	730	100

Source : Personal Survey

Regarding the satisfaction with education facilities only 21.64% respondents were satisfied with the existing facility where as 39.32% were less satisfied and 39.04% were not satisfied with facilities for education provided in their locality (Table10).

Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana :

The President of India, in his address to Parliament on 25th February 2005, announced a major plan for rebuilding rural India called Bharat Nirman. The Government has identified Rural Roads as one of the six components of Bharat Nirman and has set a goal to provide connectivity to all villages with a population of 1000 (500 in the case of hilly or tribal areas) with an all-weather road by 2009 through the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY). The item Grameen Sadak (Rural Roads) has been added with a view to give highest priority to the development and expansion of Rural Roads. as through connectivity the fruits of development can reach the rural areas.

Table 12

Response to the question “Are you satisfied with transportation facilities available in your locality, mention the level of satisfaction?”

Level	No. of Respondents	Percent
Satisfaction	452	61.92
Less satisfied	186	25.48
Not satisfied	92	12.60
Total	730	100

Source : Personal Survey

Regarding the satisfaction with Transportation facilities 61.92% respondents were satisfied with the existing facility where as 25.48% were less satisfied and 12.60% were not satisfied with facilities for transportation provided in their locality (Table 11).

Prime Minister Ujjwala Yojana-

Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana is one of the ambitious schemes of the Government of India. The scheme has been completely designed keeping women. This is a social welfare scheme. The scheme was launched by the Prime Minister on May 1, 2016 from Ballia, Uttar Pradesh. it is necessary to present the details of Ujjwala scheme. The health of rural women has been kept paramount in the scheme. Promotion of non-conventional energy sources. This scheme is for the women of BPL family.

Table 13

Response to the question “Beneficiary families for Prime Minister Ujjwala Yojana (P.U.Y)

Beneficiary families	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	267	36.57
No	463	63.43
Total	730	100.00

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question Beneficiary families for Prime Minister Ujjwala Yojana?” 36.57% respondents are yes and 63.43% respondent are no Beneficiary families for Prime Minister Ujjwala Yojana. (Table 12)

When 730 families of 16 selected village were asked through a questionnaire that through whom do you get information about the schemes related to rural development of the Government of India and the Government of Uttar Pradesh.

The main source of knowing the rural development programme

Table 14

Response to the question “Source of information Rural Development Programme

Source of information	No. of Respondents	Percent
Gram Pradhan	324	44.38
Political Worker	112	15.34
Newspaper	97	13.28
Radio and TV	92	12.60
Other source	105	14.40
Total	730	100

Source: Personal Survey

The responses of the respondents to the question “Source of Information Rural Development Programme” have been grouped into five categories i.e. Gram Pradhan, political worker, newspaper, Radio and TV and other source. It is analysed that about 44.38% respondents are Gram Pradhan, 15.34% respondents are political worker, 13.28% respondents are Newspaper, 12.60% respondents are Radio and TV and 14.40% Other source of information gain about the Rural Development Programme (Table13).

Conclusion :

The study area is rural, tribal dominant and forested region. When 730 families asked through a questionnaire that through whom do you get information about the schemes related to rural development. Over all lack of information regarding the rural development programme in village area due to illiteracy and ignorance of local people. In sonbhadra district for rural development boosting infrastructure and Connectivity, empowering livelihoods, natural resources based development, improving agriculture, health facilities, transportation facilities and education facilities.

Reference :

1. Arora, R.C. (1979): ‘Integrated Rural Development’, S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Singh, D.N. & Singh, K.N. (1985): “Perspectives on Rural Development: Some Basic issues and Approaches; in Singh, K.N. 4 Singh, D.N. (Eds) Rural Development in India, NGSI, Varanasi.
3. Singh, J. (1978) : Key Issues integrated Rural Development” F.S.H. Division, F.A.O.
4. Singh, J. (1981): Concept of Integrated Regional Development Paper Presented in Govind Ballabh Pant Social Science Institute, Allahabad (March, 25-29).
5. Ramanathan, V.V. (1948) : “Road Transport in India”, Lucknow, pp. 32-34.
6. Meenu Jain, 2011, Rural Development Programme in India. New Delhi: Deep and Deep Publications Pvt. Ltd.
7. Rajakutty, S. 2009., Rural Development Programmes and Right to Information under Panchayatiraj. Hyderabad: National institute of Rural Development.